

D8.6 Public Communication Materials I

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Executive Summary

This deliverable details the communications activities done during M1-M18 including, among others, the development of a corporate visual identity manual, print and digital dissemination and promotional materials designed, social media activity and press releases written.

It is worth noting that in order to protect the commercial interests of the industrial participants, publication of the materials has been selective.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Comunication Plan

Sharework Project communication plan aims at raising awareness on Sharework research, as well as at communicating the benefits that collaborative robotics can bring to the European industrial sector and its employees in terms of safety and ergonomics, among other.

The project's communication plan is based, on one hand, on the production of different kind of digital, printed and audiovisual materials that support the project's dissemination activities to the industrial and scientific audience and, on the other hand, the setting up and maintenance of the project's digital channels (social media and website).

1.1 Target audiences

The communication target audiences are the same as the ones defined for dissemination activities. However, communication will focus on **non-specialised audiences** with messages that can be understood by all audiences.

Figure 1: Sharework main communication and dissemination audiences

Specifically, one of the key audiences for communication activities are the **employees of the four companies that act as industrial scenarios of the project** in order to communicate the benefits of incorporating a cobot in their work environment, as well as to explain how the implementation of Sharework technologies in their workplace is going to be carried out. Specific communication materials have been produced for these stakeholder group consisting on a video explaining the changes expected to be implemented in the industrial scenarios' companies assembly lines. These videos were shown to employees using different corporative channels (e.g. NISSAN posted the video in their internal app and has shown in all screens on the production plan).

In addition, Sharework communication activities want to target **employees working in factories susceptible to introduce robots or cobots** as task assistants, as well as raise

awareness on the latest research on human robot collaboration and technology advanced to the **general public**.

1.2 Channels

Sharework’s communication tools and materials from M1-M18 have included:

All actions considered EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.

2. Communication tools and materials

2.1 Corporate visual identity

Eurecat, as the leader of Communication task has developed Shareworks’s Corporate Visual Identity, including the project’s logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to Sharework including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and some marketing and advertising materials.

2.1.1 Logotype

Sharework logo aims to represent the project’s concept of human-robot collaboration by using a half-human half-robot face in two different colours that articulate together the project’s name Sharework. The logo can be used, depending on the background colour, in the two corporate colours as can be seen below:

Figure 2: Different versions of Sharework logos (top - full-color, bottom-left - negative version, right - bicolour versions).

2.1.2 Corporate Visual Identity Manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook has been produced and distributed among partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

Partners should treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of the project's materials. See below some parts of the manual:

Figure 4: Sharework corporate colours

Figure 3: Graphic resources

Figure 6: Corporate fonts for promotional materials

Figure 5: Corporate fonts for deliverables and project presentations

2.1.3 Word Templates

Two Word templates are available for partners: one for deliverables and another one to be used for minutes, meetings' agenda and other purposes. These materials are ready to be used throughout all the project's execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

Figure 7: Deliverable template

Figure 9: Letter template

Figure 8: Agenda template

2.1.4 Power Point Template

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all project's internal and external presentations:

Figure 10: Power Point template

2.2 Promotional materials

A set of different promotional materials has been produced during M1-M18 including an infosheet (M2), leaflet (M5), rollup (M5), a general presentation and poster layout (M6). All materials follow the project visual identity guidelines and are available to all the consortium in an electronic format, so they can be used every time a partner carries out a disseminating activity, such as attending to key conferences and fairs.

2.2.1 Infosheet

An A-4 infosheet was produced one month since the beginning of the project as a promotional material to send to close partners and peer researchers. The content is based on the main objectives of the project and expected outputs.

Figure 11: View of the project's infosheet

2.2.2 Leaflet

A leaflet describing the Sharework project was elaborated during the firsts months of the project and has been updated since then with new pictures.

Figure 12: View of project's leaflet

The document contains an introduction to the project, its objectives, key outputs and system features, as well as other related information.

The project's leaflet will be periodically updated to adjust its contents to the state of the project.

2.2.3 Rollup

Design of two versions of a project rollups to be used in events.

Figure 13: View of the two versions of the rollup designed

2.2.4 Poster Layout

Production of a poster layout to be used by partners when presenting the project results in scientific conferences.

The document includes guidelines on how to structure the information along the poster.

Figure 14: View of the poster layout

2.2.5 General presentation

To support the communication of Sharework project, a power point presentation has been prepared. Each partner is able to add new slides and complete the presentation with its needs according to the event and/or audience.

Together with the leaflet and the infosheet, this presentation serves as the project business card and has been used in conferences, workshops and other events, from the beginning of the project.

Figure 15: View of Sharework power point presentation

2.3 Website

On M3, Sharework's project website was launched www.sharework-project.eu and serves as the main channel for general audience to find out more about Sharework project, displaying the project's basic information, objectives, industrial scenarios and benefits.

Furthermore, the website is the central point of entry for all public material, including promotional materials and gives access to SHAREWORK's Twitter channel.

During M1-M18, the website has been regularly updated with blog posts and information about dissemination activities.

The Sharework website has Matomo installed in the platform's back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site's performance. Since its launch in M3, the website has received **2,963 visits**, **8,010 page visits** and **2,9 actions per visit**, including page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches per visit (analysis based on M3 – website creation until April 2020).

As for geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits from M3-M17 have come from Spain (denoting EUT's own efforts disseminating it at the Spanish level). The picture seems relevant also to show that Sharework has impacted beyond EU borders. Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices.

Figure 16: Sharework statistics from Matomo

Figure 17: View of Sharework homepage

2.4 Social Media

Eurecat manages Sharework’s social media accounts and its contents described hereinafter. Sharework project has a **Twitter Channel**, [@Sharework_EU](#), and a **YouTube channel**.

On the other hand, **partners contribute spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels**, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator is responsible of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

2.4.1 Twitter

Twitter is the 2.0 tool most used by the European Commission to now disseminate the H2020 program, so the creation of an account has full meaning. The account is managed by Eurecat with the support of project partners for the correct management of the account.

Sharework's main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on the benefits of cobots and HRC for the industry, as well as promoting the project's results to key stakeholders and the broader audience. Twitter allows us to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

At M18, Sharework Twitter has **241 followers** and has generated **147 tweets** and more than **120K impressions**.

Figure 18: View of Sharework Twitter account

2.4.1.1 Account management

To feed the account Eurecat creates **bimonthly content plan** to be disseminated through Twitter. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed through this channel and can spread the word through their own channels.

Sharework's Communication Leader Eurecat uses Hootsuite for programming tweets and shorten URLs, a management tool that facilitates the publication of contents and easy monitors the activity on social media.

Comments and answers are being managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

2.4.1.2 Strategy

Sharework's Twitter account content strategy follows the guidelines below:

Content strategy includes

- Disseminate the organization of meetings, reviews, and milestones including text and photos if possible.
- Content curation: sharing news on cobots / robotics, mechatronics, industry 4.0 and robotics, industry automation, ergonomics at the workplace, HRC applied research and technologies and HRC applied to different industry sectors (especially the ones represented in the use-cases: railway, automotive industry, mechanical machining and capital goods).
- Disseminate the videos made for the project (to make the project more accessible/understandable) better reach users thanks to a character and a specific plot.
- Sharing news and blog posts published in the website to increase traffic to the website.

- To increase the reach of the tweets, it is proposed the frequent use of the following hashtags, usual in other areas within the scope of the project: #Sharework #robotics #robots #cobots #industry40 #HRC #industry #automation #ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020 #Fof_EU #FoF #HumanRobotCollaboration #CollaborativeRobotics #CollaborativeRobots
- Mention project partners when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.
- Mention and retweet content from projects funded under the same call (HR-Recycler @HrRecycler, CoLLaboratE @collaborate_eu, Fit4FoF @FIT4FoF, Integradde @Integradde, Rossini @Rossini_project, iQonic @iQonic_project, Sherlock @SherlockH2020, Oled Solar @oledsolarh2020, Floim, Manuela) and especially the ones working in the field of human-robot collaboration (CoLLaboratE, ROSSINI and SHERLOCK).

Branding strategy includes

- Twitter covering in fairs in international trade shows and fairs where Sharework is presented using the official hashtag of the event (e.g. Advanced Factories #AF2019, the European Robotics Forum #ERF2019, Global Robot Expo #GREX19, the International Conference on Robotics and Automation #ICRA2019, etc.).
- Sharework's Twitter official account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project.

Influencers strategy includes

- Regularly mention @EU_H2020 @EuScienceInnov @eu_Robotics @CORDIS_EU @EU_commission @EFFRA_life in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Identify and mention influencers in the field of collaborative robots, mechatronics and research on HRC, etc.
- Identification of stakeholder's accounts to promote follow-back and to increase the number of Sharework followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

2.4.1.3 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure Twitter's KPIs (*please view Communication KPIs section for more information*) and other data about the account activity.

2.4.2 Youtube

A YouTube account was created on M10. [Sharework YouTube Channel](#) has been used as a video content repository and its content links have been shared on social media and through Sharework's website.

So far, it has 7 videos published publicly on each industrial scenario (ALSTOM, CEMBRE, NISSAN and GOIZPER).

Figure 19: View of Sharework YouTube account

2.4.3 Partners' social media

Partners also share Sharework news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook mainly), including press releases, notices about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.sharework-project.eu or in Sharework's twitter account.

From M1-M18, partners have posted a total of 47 tweets in their corporate social media accounts, which got 362 likes and 151 retweets.

Figure 20: Examples of Tweets published in partner's corporate accounts

Regarding to **LinkedIn**, Sharework partners have published **16 posts**, accounting for **134 likes** and **4 comments**.

This strategy allows to reach directly target audiences from validated professional accounts that are already networked with them.

Figure 21: Examples of posts published on partners' LinkedIn accounts

The corporate accounts being used for spreading the word on Sharework news are:

PARTNER			
Eurecat	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecat.org/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/
ALSTOM	https://www.facebook.com/ALSTOM	@Alstom	https://www.linkedin.com/company/alstom/
NISSAN	https://www.facebook.com/NissanESP	@Nissan_ESP	NA
CNR	https://www.facebook.com/UfficioStampaCnr	@StampaCnr	NA
STAM	NA	@Stam_Tech	https://www.linkedin.com/company/stam-s-r-l/
CEMBRE	NA	NA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cembre-s-p-a/
MCM	NA	NA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/mcm-spa/
FRAUNHOFER	https://de-de.facebook.com/FraunhoferIWU/	@Fraunhofer_IWU	NA

<u>RWTH</u>	https://www.facebook.com/IGMR.RWTH/	NA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/igmr/
<u>TUDA</u>	https://www.facebook.com/Alumni-TU-Darmstadt-171149852998742/	NA	https://www.linkedin.com/school/technische-universitaet-darmstadt/
<u>GOIZPER</u>	NA	@goizpergroup	https://www.linkedin.com/company/goizper/
<u>STRANE</u>	NA	@Strane_Innov	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/strane-innovation
<u>LMS</u>	NA	@LMSUPATRAS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/laboratory-for-manufacturing-systems-and-automation/
<u>INTRA</u>	NA	@INTRASOFT_Int	https://www.linkedin.com/company/intrasoft-international/
<u>UNE</u>	NA	@NormasUNE	https://es.linkedin.com/company/une-asociaci3n-espa1ola-de-normalizaci3n

2.5 Press releases and articles

During M1-M18, partners have produced several press releases regarding the participation of partners in Sharework project developments and results and scientific advances and meetings.

The consortium has produced a total of **2 general press releases** which were distributed to all partners and adapted to several languages:

- **January 2019** - *The Sharework project to create new technology for human-robot collaboration in the industry* <https://sharework-project.eu/the-sharework-project-will-create-new-technology-for-human-robot-collaboration-in-the-industry/>
- **December 2019** - Joint press release with other EU projects working on Collaborative Robotics that participated in the Workshop of the Cluster “Future of Industrial Collaborative Robotics”
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5bf59e007c9327b9f9aef60a/t/5dee1acb9778c378d7e00d60/1575885515885/HRC+Projects+Joint+Press+Release.pdf>

In addition, Eurecat, in collaboration with Nissan, produced 3 country-focused press releases:

- **November 2019** – *Nissan starts 45 R+D and Industry 4.0 projects with Eurecat* <https://eurecat.org/nissan-endegara-45-projectes-innovacio-tecnologica-industria-4-0-eurecat/>
- **March 2020** - *A new system to improve workers’ security and ergonomics (in Spanish)* <https://eurecat.org/es/nuevo-sistema-inteligente-mejorara-seguridad-priorizara-ergonomia-trabajos-con-robots/>

- **March 2020** – *Eurecat shows the potential of the hybridization of digital and industrial technologies* (in Spanish) <https://eurecat.org/eurecat-mostra-potencial-hibridacio-tecnologies-digitals-industrials/>

Articles and press releases have had a great impact on online and print media. A clipping study covering the project period shows that currently up to **39 articles in Spanish and Italian print and online media outlets have been published.**

This accounts for a total audience of 42,558,090 which translates on an Economic Value of 475,377€.

2.6 Videos

Partners have produced a series of audio-visual materials on each of the industrial scenarios (ALSTOM, NISSAN, GOIZPER and CEMBRE) to be published and shared from all project communication channels (website, social media) and partners' corporate channels.

The videos aim to explain each industrial case briefly, how Sharework technology will be implemented in their assembly or subassembly lines and the benefits of implementing Sharework to their production line. The videos combine images of each industrial scenario and some quotes from each company representatives.

As requested by Spanish partners, the videos for ALSTOM, NISSAN and GOIZPER use case have been translated into Spanish. All videos have subtitles to be able to follow the explanations from company representatives easily.

Videos produced:

- [CEMBRE - Human-Robot Collaboration at the load/unload stations of logistic manufacturing systems](#)
- [GOIZPER industrial scenario - HRC for operators assistance on intermittent indexing units' assembly](#)
- [ALSTOM industrial scenario – Human-Robot Collaboration to improve trains' manufacturing processes](#)
- [NISSAN Industrial Scenario - Human-Robot Collaboration during Door Assembly Into the Vehicle](#)

3. KPIs Communication activities

Strategy	Indicator	Means verification	of	M1-April 2020	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings		4	>8
	Number of articles, sector press with project acknowledgements	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings		39	>50
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytis		2,963	>4.500
	Number Pages Viewed			8,010	>10.000
	Number page / session			2,9	>1.5
	Number users			1,866	>2.000
	Avg. session time			3 min 29s	>1.50 min
Social Media (Twitter)	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics		241	>150
	Number Tweets			141	>200
	Twitter Impressions			119,000	>50.000
	Number mentions			82	>20
Social Media (Mentions in partners accounts).	Number of posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)		62	>20
	Number of Likes			496	>50
	Number Shares / Retweets			151	>10

4. ANNEX

4.1 List of articles published in online and print media outlets

4.1.1 Online media

Date	Media	Title	Audience	Economic Value	Link
13/03/20	Automatica e instrumentacion	La automoción marca el camino de la fábrica conectada	3602	7,2	Link
11/03/20	TecnoNews	Impulsar el trabajo conjunto entre operarios y robots	1000	1	Link
06/03/20	Factoria del Futuro	Un sistema inteligente priorizará la ergonomía de los trabajos con robots	1000	1	Link
06/03/20	InterEmpresas Net	Un nuevo sistema inteligente mejorará la seguridad y priorizará la ergonomía de los trabajos con robots	64343	308,84	Link
05/03/20	Noticias de Gipuzkoa	Goizper participa en un proyecto de interacción entre robots y empleados	NA	NA	Link
04/03/20	elconfidencial.com	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	974769	4971,32	Link
04/03/20	ABC.es	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	1383153	8298,92	Link
04/03/20	Mundoplast.com	Eurecat participa en Advanced Factories 2020	1000	1	Link
04/03/20	La Vanguardia	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	1527887	7792,22	Link
03/03/20	Factoria del Futuro	Eurecat muestra la hibridación de las tecnologías digitales e industriales	1000	1	Link
19/11/19	Mundoplast.com	Nissan y Eurecat colaboran en innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0	93	0,19	Link
13/11/19	Tool-Maker.net	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	278	1,11	Link
13/11/19	TecnoNews	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica con Eurecat	186	0,37	Link
08/11/19	Smart-Lighting.es	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de digitalización e industria 4.0 en sus plantas de producción	616	1,23	Link
06/11/19	Factoria del Futuro	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de industria 4.0 de la mano de Eurecat	1000	n/d	Link
05/11/19	Redes Telecoms	Digitalización e Industria 4.0 en Nissan	155	0,31	Link
05/11/19	VilaWeb	Nissan i Eurecat emprendran 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica i indústria 4.0	82536	321,89	Link
05/11/19	La República	Nissan i Eurecat emprendran 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica i indústria 4.0	12345	37,04	Link
05/11/19	Europa Press	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	271412	1954,17	Link
05/11/19	Gente Digital	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	6171	24,69	Link
05/11/19	Actualitat Diària	Nissan i Eurecat uneixen els seus sinèrgies en 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica fins a 2022	155	0,31	Link

05/11/19	CastellonInformacion.com	Nissan y Eurecat unen sus sinergías en 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica hasta 2022	6171	12,34	Link
05/11/19	Motor Tenerife	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	213	0,43	Link
05/11/19	InterEmpresas Net	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e Industria 4.0 con Eurecat	86034	387,15	Link
05/11/19	Metalindustria	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	null	n/d	Link
05/11/19	MSN Spain	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	34689536	409336,51	Link
10/10/19	mc mutual	INDUSTRIA 4.0 Y ROBÓTICA COLABORATIVA. EL FUTURO YA ESTÁ AQUÍ	1232	2,46	Link
23/07/19	El Periodico de Cataluña	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico para la colaboración hombre-robot	939320	5325,94	Link
18/05/19	Giornale di Brescia	Sharework: la svolta dei robot passa da Cembre	36206	260,69	Link
30/01/19	TecnoNews	Proyecto europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	309	0,618	Link
28/01/19	InterEmpresas Net	@Eurecat_news Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	45910	220,362	Link
27/01/19	Prevecionar	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	10492	40,92	Link
24/01/19	CIC Construcción	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	616	1,232	Link
24/01/19	Tool-Maker.net	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	62	0,124	Link
23/01/19	La Vanguardia	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico para la colaboración hombre-robot	1544680	9453,441	Link

4.1.2 Print media

Media	Readers	Circulation	Diffusion	Title	Date	Economic Value	Link
La Razón Innovadores	229000	83954	58768	ESCAPARATE DE IDEAS	15/03/20	2384,71	Link
Automática e Instrumentación	19608	5017	4902	LA AUTOMOCIÓN MARCA EL CAMINO DE LA FÁBRICA CONECTADA	01/02/20	18484,23	Link
Técnica y Tecnología para la Automoción	1000	250	250	NISSAN EMPRENDERÁ 45 PROYECTOS DE INNOVACIÓN TECNOLÓGICA E INDUSTRIA 4.0 CON EURECAT	01/11/19	4380	Link
GIORNALE DI BRESCIA	null	0	0	Sharework: la nuova frontiera dei robot passa da Cembre	18/05/19	n/d	Link
La Vanguardia (Ed. Català) - Suplement	615000	52125	42687	NUEVO PROYECTO EUROPEO	31/01/19	1362,66	Link

